

INDEPENDENT WORK EDUCATIONALLY - REPETITION, STRENGTHENING AND DEEPENING OF THEORETICAL KNOWLEDGE AND PRACTICAL SKILLS

¹Kazimova Nafisaxon Minovarovna, ²Adildjonovoy Muzifabonu Abbasxon kizi

¹Associate Professor of Gosudarstvennogo pedagogical institute imeni

Mukimi, Kokand city, Uzbekistan

²Student of Gosudarstvennogo pedagogicheskogo instituta imeni

Mukimi, Kokand city, Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *This article focuses on independent thinking, independent research, determining the student's level of knowledge, working on oneself with the help of factors that affect the student's mental activity. Information is given about the independent work of students, which is done without a teacher, but at the appointed time based on his ingenuity and research.*

Keywords: *monologue, dialogue, heuristic, search, research, programmed tasks.*

Education is carried out in the course of students' educational activities. Such activity is carried out by the student's participation in the lesson, his relationship with the teacher and other people, independent work, independent thinking, personal reaction in different situations, with the help of factors that affect the student's behavior and mental activity, among which independent work is special. becomes important. Independent work of students is work that is done without the direct participation of the teacher, but based on his ingenuity and research.

Independent work methods help to coordinate the educational, educational and developmental tasks of teaching [1].

Independent work educationally - theoretical knowledge serves to repeat, strengthen and deepen practical skills.

In the educational sense, they form and educate individual qualities such as independence, hard work, and responsibility. It helps the development of independent work, thinking, skills and abilities, trains the individual's will. These teaching methods are of great importance in preparing students to continue their studies for independent work.

Independent work can be used for performing some exercises, checking various tasks, finding answers to questions, and even studying the whole chapter independently.

The following was considered necessary to enable students to do independent work:

- formation of necessary skills and qualifications for students to work with textbooks, books, references;

- improving students' reading, writing, calculation and other activities;

- to distinguish basic concepts from non-basic concepts and to form self-control skills;

- giving instructions to students about the rules of homework;

- creation of special methods of quick assistance in performing independent work;

- encouraging, engaging and evaluating students who have completed independent work;

Pupils should combine their educational activities during the lesson with independent work. The effectiveness of the lesson depends not only on the presentation of new material, but also on the students' ability to receive assignments and solve them independently. It is

noteworthy that independent works are continued after the lesson. Independent work of students in chemistry is carried out during the course of the lesson and in extracurricular activities. This situation shows the continuity of the education system. The fact that independent work is important for students to gain deep knowledge has been proven once again in the experimental work process.

Among the general methods, various aspects of the teacher's activity are important in the organization of independent educational activities of students. The lesson can be organized mainly on the basis of the following didactic methods. Of these, the first three types are related to the presentation of educational material by the teacher, and the next three types are related to the organization of independent educational activities of students. These are: monologue, dialogue, heuristic, search, research, programmed task methods. [2]

One of the independent learning methods of students is to organize independent learning activities for students to analyze the facts and materials presented and discover the essence of new concepts and methods of activity.

The method of research consists of independent analysis of the stated factual materials rather than providing information in the form of a teacher's conversation, as well as organizing the activity of students to discover the essence of new concepts and methods of activity.

The essence of the research method is that the discovery of new laws and regulations is not carried out by the teacher with the participation of students, but under the guidance of the teacher and with his help, the students themselves do it independently.

The research method is to describe the educational material in dialog form:

- a) use of some issues and assignments when explaining new knowledge;
- b) questions for analyzing and summarizing the educational material and giving assignments;
- c) application of issues related to knowledge for smaller research, conclusions proving, rejecting wrong ideas;
- g) to organize detailed discussions on independent knowledge of topics.

The use of such methods under the guidance of the teacher is of great importance in the independent acquisition of knowledge by students and in the formation of independent work skills and qualifications in terms of time and in terms of the size of the educational material.

Students can do the following independent tasks in chemistry classes:

1. Study the text of the topic in the textbook.
2. Performing exercises related to the given topic.
3. Solving experimental and computational problems.
4. Solving independent test tasks.
5. Conducting experiments and observations.
6. Work with tables and schemes.
7. Working with visual aids and other educational tools.
8. Studying materials related to the topic with the help of a computer.
9. Use of Internet materials in studying the topic.
10. Solving chemical puzzles, riddles and various individual tasks.

Regardless of the type, independent work is carried out with the help of certain questions and assignments.

Tasks are usually arranged from simple to complex, and each task is directed to the realization of a certain didactic goal. Separate types of independent work are interrelated and can be combined under certain conditions [3].

For example, performing chemical experiments can be done frontally. In this case, the activity of the students will have a copy character, and the experiments will be conducted in order to strengthen the learned material.

It is important to increase the cognitive activity of students in the organization of independent work in the lesson.

New knowledge is well understood only if students understand the problem and are interested in the work to be done. When setting goals and tasks, it is necessary to take into account the desire of students to be independent, express themselves, and thirst for knowledge. If conditions are created to satisfy these needs in the lesson, students will start working with interest.

Increasing interest in learning is a complex issue, and the result of students' effectiveness in the educational process depends on how this issue is resolved. In pedagogy and psychology, there are general views on the formation of students' interest in learning.

In order to increase interest in learning, it is important to teach how to see novelty in familiar things, to slowly and gradually raise students from the level of elementary, simple knowledge to the level of drawing scientific concepts and conclusions. Interest in knowledge awakens when talking about the history of scientific discoveries, the struggle of ideas, the work of scientists and the use of substances in life. The study material of the chemistry course provides such opportunities.

Psychologists say that the activation of educational activities develops interest in learning. The activation of the teaching process is achieved by the use of various independent works organized according to the characteristics of the students' interests and specific educational goals.

The teacher considers various aspects of the methodology, taking into account the importance of generating interest in knowledge from the beginning of the lesson. The most important of them refer to 3 situations: firstly, to focus students' attention on the goals and tasks of the lesson; secondly, to arouse interest in the content of the repeated and newly studied material; thirdly, to ensure that students get into a form of work that is interesting for them.

Active perception of new material takes place in classes where issues related to problematic situations of formation of students' chemical thinking are discussed. In this pedagogical situation, an environment of research is created, in which students begin to more actively solve the problems set before them [5].

Repetition of the learned material can also be the basis for the emergence and strengthening of interest in knowledge and attract attention to the most important part of the studied material.

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